

HOME MEAL PLANNING, PREPARATION, MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND THE PERSONAL WELL-BEING OF GRADE 10 STUDENTS

CHRISTIAN HENRY D. CAMO¹

JOCELYN V. MADRIDEO²

christianhenryd.camo@gmail.com¹

jocelyn.madrideo@lspu.edu.ph²

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6628-3400>

Laguna State Polytechnic University- San Pablo Campus

ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the relationship of home meal planning, preparation, management practices and personal well-being of grade 10 students. Specifically, it looks into the perception of the respondents in home meal planning, home meal preparation home meal management practices, personal well-being and the test of relationship between home meal planning, preparation, management practices and personal well-being of grade 10 students. The respondents of the study are all grade 10 students of Bagupaye National High School, Mulanay Quezon composed of 138 students. A combination of constructed and adapted questionnaire is the main instrument of this study and undergo assessment and validation of the experts. This study utilize a descriptive-correlational research design since it involves in knowing the prevailing condition of a thing or event. More so, correlational research is applied in the study to establish relationship between two or among more variables. The data collected are statistically treated through the use of weighted mean, standard deviation and pearson r. Based from the results, respondents perceive “great extent” on budget allocation and availability of ingredients and resources, however respondents “moderately observed dietary requirements and lifestyle and allergy concern. They also perceive buying food, food preparation, cooking and storing foods as with great extent, the same thing with food budget and managing leftovers. Meanwhile, students perceive food safety and sanitation as with “very great extent”. Likewise, respondents perceive their personal well-being as “with great extent”. The home meal planning, preparation, management practices related variables show all significant correlation in the personal well-being of grade 10 students in terms of physical, social, emotional, environmental and intellectual.

Keywords: Meal Management Practices Meal planning, Meal preparation, Personal Well-Being